

**Hochschule
Augsburg** University of
Applied Sciences

**Faculty of
Computer
Sciences**

Research report

Field of study
Master of Applied Research
in Computer Science (M.Sc.)

Michael Fürmann

Setting up CI/CD for JavaScript Web Applications with GitLab and Docker

Supervisor: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Alexandra Teynor

Date of Submission: 29.03.2019

Hochschule für angewandte
Wissenschaften Augsburg
University of Applied Sciences

An der Hochschule 1
D-86161 Augsburg

Phone +49 821 55 86-0
Fax +49 821 55 86-3222

www.hs-augsburg.de
info@hs-augsburg.de

Faculty of Computer Sciences
Phone +49 821 55 86-3450
Fax +49 821 55 86-3499

Author:
Michael Fürmann
Jahnstr. 10
86316 Friedberg
Phone +49 821 604901
michael.fuermann@hs-augsburg.de

Setting up CI/CD for JavaScript Web Applications with GitLab and Docker

Michael Fürmann

Augsburg, 29. March 2019

Contents

Abstract	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Demand	7
3. Deploying the JavaScript application	9
3.1. Manual Deployment	10
3.2. Automated with Continuous Integration and Delivery/Deployment . . .	11
4. Running the web application	14
4.1. On Premise	14
4.2. Software as a Service	15
4.3. Software as a Service On-Premise	16
5. Software Stack for deployment automation	17
5.1. GitLab and GitLab CI	18
5.2. Docker	19
6. CI/CD with GitLab CI and docker	22
6.1. Prerequisites	22
6.2. Defining the Stages for the CI Pipeline	24
6.2.1. Testing of new code	26
6.2.2. Deploying of the source code	27
6.2.3. Building the app image	30

6.2.4. Deploying the release candidate	32
6.2.5. Signing the image as stable for production	34
6.2.6. Deploying the app to production	35
7. Conclusion	36
7.1. Matching requirements and approach	37
7.2. What to automate, or not	38
7.3. Outlook	40
A. Appendix	41
A.1. GitLab CI configuration	41
A.2. Compose definitions for running the application	45
A.3. Dockerfiles for building node server and application images	48
References	49

Abstract

Software development teams working with agile methods want to improve discussions regarding new features and satisfy their customer by releasing new versions of their software as early and as often as possible. If not done with the right strategy, the deployment of a web application can become a time-consuming and error-prone task, that is neither reliable, repeatable nor executable for deployments on a short interval. If in addition tight security requirements of the customer with regard to the secure productive operation are added, deployment becomes a risk to keep the best developers of the team busy for a long time.

To solve this difficulty, approaches known as Continuous Integration (CI), Delivery (CDE) and Deployment (CD) describe techniques to test and deploy software changes in a highly automated manner. Additionally, using established cloud server techniques for virtualisation and code signing provides new possibilities for deployments on restricted systems that meet higher security demands even for projects dealing with sensitive personal information.

With a suitable set of tools, a team of developers can accomplish tests and deliveries/deployments, that are fully automated and not only fit their development process but also meet the client's security requirements. This work shows an approach how such a system can be set up, and gives recommendations on how to support the development process and deploy tested software frequent, reliable, and repeatable in different stages of development, from feature test releases to production, using GitLab and Docker.

1. Introduction

Figure 1: About 18% of developers don't deploy their software as often as desired, 71% would like to deploy new releases at least on a weekly basis (Sauce Labs; Dimensional Research 2018)

In 2019, a significant amount of companies and teams adopt methods from agile software development to their production process. According to a recent study by TEKSystems, 11% of companies worldwide expect to be evaluating the use of agile methods by end of the year 2019, whilst another 63% intend to be working agile by then (TEKsystems 2018). Regarding the principles behind the agile manifesto¹, this increases the importance of having early and continuously deployment of working software releases to satisfy the customer and support an effective feedback loop. But as shown by Figure 1, deploying new releases in the desired frequency is still not feasible for some developers. (Sauce Labs; Dimensional Research 2018)

¹<https://agilemanifesto.org/principles.html>

A successful process for application deployment must meet requirements of the development team and its actual development process, factors that vary much for different software projects. This work uses the research and development project SMILe² for discussion and the concrete application of a secure, automated deployment process.

This joint project of University Basel, University of Applied Sciences Augsburg and University Hospital Freiburg aims to improve the follow-up care of patients after an allogeneic stem cell transplantation. In the planned manner, the created application is a vital support for the patients further recovery. It is intended to be a reliable source of information on how to interpret, rate, and influence disease-related symptoms. The patient will further be encouraged to record daily parameters as weight, body temperature and blood pressure and information on important symptoms. Critical health deteriorations, that are detectable by simple rules (e.g. too high temperature, too much loss of weight) will lead to an immediate request to the user to contact the clinic. For further manual diagnosis and monitoring of the patients' recovery process, all information the user commits, shall be stored on the server.

Figure 2: Four tier development and deployment process in project SMILe: Developers implement features, merge done work to a common code base with deployment to a development server, create a release candidate on sprint end with deployment to a staging server and deploy a new version to production after approval of the project maintainer

²<https://www.hs-augsburg.de/Informatik/Projekt-SMILe.html>

The developers contributing to this project already work in an agile process. Working in a 4-tier model as described in Figure 2, every feature or change is developed in a separate feature code base (Feature, tier 1), reviewed and merged into the common development code base and deployed to a development server for testing and debugging (Dev, tier 2). On the end of a sprint iteration, code gets merged from the development to master code base, deployed to a production-like staging server, reviewed and tested as release candidate (Master, tier 3). After final approval, the release candidate is released as a new version of the application and deployed into production (Release, tier 4).

In section 2, this work first analyses the requirements of this example development team and its customer from the healthcare sector to the deployment of the example web application. After that, the sections 3 and 4 present different strategies on deploying and running a JavaScript web application in terms of the project context. Introducing to the applied part of this work, section 5 explains the tools used to implement the proposed automated CI/CDE process for the project SMILe as explained in section 6. Finally, section 7 summarises the findings of this work by comparing the proposed solution to the demands of developers and customers as listed in section 2, and suggests topics for future works.

2. Demand

Figure 3: 4-tier development process in GIT with separate branches for feature implementation (Feature), feature merging in development (Dev), Release candidates (master) and tagged commits as approved releases

As mentioned in section 1, development and deployment in a 4-tier process requires several code bases to track changes on every tier. To accomplish this in the development workflow, the team working on the example project uses specific GIT branches and GIT tags for approved releases as demonstrated by Figure 3. New features are implemented in separate feature branches of the GIT repository and merged to a common development branch upon completion. On end of each sprint the code changes get merged to the master branch, representing a release candidate. After manual review, the project maintainer adds a git tag to the last commit of the release candidate to mark a new version for release. As further conventions in this workflow, direct commits to the Dev branch are only allowed for urgent bug fixes and code merges to other branches are only permitted, if the test suite in the project executes without failures for the new code (marked by a green check in the figure).

For deployments in production, the clinic, working with sensitive patient and healthcare information, adds further demands in controlling access to the server and data storage. Furthermore, deploying an application for healthcare purpose, adds high demands on ensuring the trustworthiness of the deployed code.

For the example Project SMILe, requirements have been identified as listed below. The discussion in section 7.1 will compare this list of demands to the implementation proposed by section 6.

Demands by developers

D-1 Support the teams development process

Lowering the workload of the team executing the required actions for following the planned process leaves more time for developers to work on the application itself.

D-2 Enforce the teams development process

Having barriers to prevent accidental glitches of team members in the development process reduces confusions and danger for broken releases.

D-3 Test early and often

Code written and merged by the developers has to be tested as early as possible and for every single change. This helps the team to detect errors as soon as possible.

D-4 Deploy as early and often as possible

Deployment releases and production-like releases help to test and review new features and support discussions with the customer.

D-5 Little manual effort in deployment

Leave more time for developing the application by having less time consuming deployments

D-6 Deployment process stages fitting the development process

The 4-tier development process from section 1 should be mapped into a 4-tier deployment process foreseeing different actions for features, development releases, production-like release candidates and production deployment.

(Jez Humble 2010, p.9ff)

Demands by customer**C-1 Restricted administrative server access**

In a clinical data centre, SSH access even to external reachable servers requires VPN dial in with multi-factor authentication.

C-2 Administrative control over production systems

Administrators of the customer's data centre require full administrative control over production servers to ensure system security, stability, and backups.

C-3 Independence from operating system

Because the server system is operated by the customer himself, the operating system running on the production server must fit into his remaining server infrastructure.

C-4 Data storage and backup on premise

Working with sensitive patient data, all information stored by the application needs to stay in the customer's data centre.

C-5 Ensure trusted application state

Because deploying the application via an insecure medium like the internet, the deployment process needs to ensure the trustworthiness of the deployed application.

3. Deploying the JavaScript application

When it comes to the deployment of a web application, it is to be distinguished, whether the application is deployed for the first time or updated in production. Both scenarios differ in the difficulties a developer has to manage during the deployment process.

This section describes two different ways of deploying an application, either manually or using an automated Continuous Delivery process, showing their advantages and disadvantages considering the previously named deployment scenarios.

3.1. Manual Deployment

For the manual deployment of an application, there is a sequence of steps to be made by a developer (or a development team) by hand. These steps differ in detail for each project, but superordinate they consist of the actions listed below.

1. Create a release package
2. Move files to the server
3. Install or update dependencies
4. Migrate the database
5. Clear / regenerate caches on the server side (e.g. generated assets)
6. Restart the application server

To be executed successfully, this process needs to be well documented and be done by developers with a significant degree of expertise. Unfortunately, documentation, as a complex collaboration between multiple developers in a team, tend to be either incomplete or outdated. Besides that, manual deployment is a repetitive and boring task including lots of potential errors coming from untested code or changed but undocumented requirements, that will require an experts decisions during deployment. For example, updating an application might require to merge changes for new, modified and deleted source code files, the database migration might not work for the production database or the application server might not restart after the deployment due to a not documented requirement for a new system library. (Jez Humble 2010, P.6-7)

Because all these actions are performed by humans and thus are prone to human error, the manual deployment process is neither reliable nor repeatable. Regardless of the success of the deployment, this makes it very hard to find and document problems revealed during deployment for further investigation. Even in a 4-tier deployment

model as shown in section 1, there may still appear unforeseen problems deploying the application on the next tier. Thus, to get a more reliable and audible deployment process for enrolling and updating an application, the number of manual actions should be as low as possible. (Jez Humble 2010, P.6-7)

3.2. Automated with Continuous Integration and Delivery/Deployment

Making use of Continuous Integration (CI), by running automated tests and building the application for every code change in the repository, developers can ensure, that the whole code base is tested at any time. As prerequisite for subsequent deployment, CI can prevent the release of faulty application code into production.

While having CI in place might be good advice for most projects, the applicability of automated deployment strategies is highly impacted by the underlying development process and the desired deployment frequency. With Continuous Deployment (CD), every change of the application code gets deployed into production with no manual interference. Dependent on the developers' commit rate and workflow, multiple deployments per day are realistic. Continuous Delivery (CDE) on the other hand still requires manual actions at some steps of the process, e.g. for approving a new release after manual testing, and thus cannot reach a deployment frequency as high as CD. Figure 4 compares a process example for CI/CD and CI/CDE. (Shahin et al. 2017)

Still, both deployment approaches, combined with testing and building to CI/CD or CI/CDE, empower software developers to deploy tested, working prototypes of their software fast and with as little manual work as possible. This massively reduces the required time and effort for delivery of the web application into staging and production. In result, a more effective feedback loop with the customer can be established for maximising the quality of the deployed software. (Jez Humble 2010, P.10ff)

To achieve a successful deployment automation, it is vital to plan the process for testing the application and deploying it to the desired target systems. Reacting on every code change in the project, this process' goal is to automate required actions as testing, building and deploying on every tier in the teams committed development process

Figure 4: Comparison of a fully automated CD to CDE requiring a manual approval of new releases

as much as possible. This requires a lot more prior knowledge about structure and deployment of the application than the previous introduced manual process, where an expert can still intervene on occurring problems or unforeseen circumstances during the process. (Jez Humble 2010, P.10ff)

Figure 5 shows a process plan for deployment automation in the example project SMILE, that was introduced in section 1. This is a CI/CDE process, as it still contains manual steps from the introduced development process for merging code to higher tier branches or approving a new release by tagging a commit. (Shahin et al. 2017)

In the most simple way, the planned process automation is set up by a collection of scripts, executing pre-defined commands for code changes in the different tiers of the development process. But there are also language or model-based solutions for setting up CI/CD(E). These mainly differ in time and knowledge that is required to implement the process and scalability for projects with growing complexity. Even if the next sections focus on a script based approach (based on the solution provided by GitLab, see section 5.1), all mentioned approaches provide the team with a fine granular documentation for reliable and repeatable tests and deployments as showed in section 6.2. Using CI/CD can further inform the developers, whether the current code is functional and reliable (section 6.2.1), automatically create signed builds (sections

Figure 5: CI/CDE plan for the 4 tier development workflow introduced in Figure 2 and 3

6.2.3 and 6.2.5) and deploy the application to the target servers (sections 6.2.2, 6.2.4 and 6.2.6). Thus, the developers can focus more on creating the software instead of handling the deployment of code changes. (Talwar et al. 2005)

As stated, compared to manual deployment, the use of CI/CD(E) requires a lot more planning and setting up in advance. But on the other hand it offers automated code tests as well as reliable and repeatable deployments. Thus, the effort for setting up a working CI/CD(E) process should be taken in software projects of any size to empower the team to concentrate more on creating the software and establishing an efficient feedback loop with the customer based on frequent releases while leaving boring and repeatedly tasks to an automated CI/CD(E) pipeline. (Jez Humble 2010, P.10ff)

4. Running the web application

For running a web application in production there are several very different approaches. The range begins with deploying “On-Premise” directly on the customer’s own servers or deploying it as “Software as a Service” (SaaS) on the developer’s servers. The upper end is marked by the usage of a cloud application platform service like Google App Engine³ or Heroku⁴ (Platform as a Service, PaaS) for deployment or even orchestrating a whole virtual infrastructure as “Infrastructure as a Service” (IaaS) on cloud computing platforms like Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2)⁵. (Bibi et al. 2012, P.1)

Because in the SMILe project, deployment flexibility is needed on one hand, on the other the customer demands controlled storage, the sections below focus on the approaches On-Premise and SaaS. PaaS and IaaS, that heavily rely on servers and storage controlled by a third party are inappropriate or would require a lot more work on security mechanisms to meet this data security policy. Therefore, sections 4.1 and 4.2 describe the main attributes of the approaches On-Premise and SaaS, along with benefits and caveats while section 4.3 shows an example for a combination to gain the best out of both.

4.1. On Premise

Running an application or a service On-Premise means to run it completely on the customer’s site and his own, self-managed servers. This way, the customer has full control over physical and virtual access to the server and storage systems as well as secured backups. This is the most trustworthy solution for running an application for the customer. That might be the reason, why even coming with a much bigger amount of administrative work and higher cost for IT systems(ibid., P.2), many customers still decide not to use cloud-based services for certain applications. As revealed by an Eurostat Model Questionnaire in 2016, illustrated by Figure 6, this is all the more true for business-critical assets and applications like CRM or accounting software.

³<https://cloud.google.com/appengine/>

⁴<https://www.heroku.com/>

⁵<https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/>

Figure 6: More business-critical assets and applications are less often moved to cloud services

(Eurostat 2018)

Because IT systems on the customer's site should usually be well-secured from external access, external developers often have no or very limited access to these systems. Having further no administrative control of the operating system used, libraries installed on the server or specific database settings makes the deployment process of applications rather unpredictable. Thus, manual deployment as described in section 3.1 might be the preferred method over automation using CI/CD (see section 3.2) in the last tier of the development process.

4.2. Software as a Service

Offering software as a service, the developer takes care of the full hosting of the application, selling only the pure usage of the software to his clients. On the side of the customer, this reduces the complexity of his own IT environment, for not having to provide and maintain his own servers for running the applications. This includes

carrying for secure and available data storage as well as high availability server setups for critical applications. Furthermore, bought or leased standard software from a SaaS provider is almost immediately available for use instead of being installed on any servers On-Premise first. (Bibi et al. 2012, P.2)

So far, SaaS seems to be a clear win for the customer (apart from self-controlled data storage) but bringing more work for developers for running and maintaining the server infrastructure. However, compared to the findings from section 4.1 leading to prefer manual deployment for On-Premise hosted applications, there are real benefits for the developer in the SaaS approach, too. Not only the system and run time specifications for development tier releases of the application are set by the developer, he also has full control over the environment on which the application is run in production. Therefore, it is possible to determine the exact steps for deploying on every tier from dev to release (see figure 5) in advance and thus create a reliable and repeatable deployment process as shown in section 6.

4.3. Software as a Service On-Premise

As mentioned in section 4.1, running an application On-Premise is great to fulfil a customer's demand on data security and privilege restriction for external users but unfortunately is a hindrance for automated deployments. SaaS (see section 4.2) on the other hand, while allowing the developer to deploy frequent and automated on his servers at any time may not match the customer's security policy that requires data storage On-Premise or restricted application access within the corporate firewall. The approach presented in the following attempts to meet the demands of both parties.

Figure 7: 76% of companies worldwide already operate their own private cloud On-Premise
(451 Research 2017)

The growing amount of deployed private clouds in enterprise IT infrastructures, as shown in figure 7, adds the possibility to melt both approaches to a kind of “Software as a Service On-Premise”, gaining benefits from On-Premise and SaaS for customer and developer. On a system operated on the customer’s site, that offers either containerisation or virtualisation technology, the developer needs just enough access and privileges to enrol, update and restart a specific containerised or virtualised application. Out of many appropriate software solutions, this work focuses on containerisation technologies by using Docker as described in section 5.2 because of the possible double use as job runner for GitLab CI as described in section 5.1.

Using those containerisation techniques for deployment On-Premise offers advantages from both previously mentioned approaches. The customer operates the application in his own data centre. Thus he has full administrative control of the servers, data storage, and backups and even the accessibility of the application through his own network firewall. On the other hand it allows the developer to build and test images containing the full application on his development servers for deployment on the customer’s private cloud servers (see section 6.2.3). Using container images, he has full control over the system- and runtime-environment the application will be executed in, independent and unaffected from the host server infrastructure. Further, images can be code signed after creation to ensure they are transferred unmodified to the production servers over the internet.

This way, reliable deployments and updates of the application can be accomplished with very few access privileges for the developer to the production server infrastructure. It also meets the customer’s requirements on data security while still allowing automation with CI/CD as shown in section 6.2.6.

5. Software Stack for deployment automation

To meet the demands for automated tests and deployments (as outlined in section 2) using a SaaS On-Premise approach as described in the previous section, a development team needs a software stack, offering the following abilities.

- keep track of the current code state in the different development tiers
- trigger required actions if any code of the application is changed in any of the tiers
- Target systems to run the app meeting requirements for the different development tiers

The team in the previously introduced project SMILe uses GitLab and Docker to meet these requirements to the software stack. This section introduces both software solutions whilst section 6 proposes an attempt on how to automate tests and deployment using this stack for JavaScript web applications.

5.1. GitLab and GitLab CI

Once started as a graphical web interface to GIT repositories⁶ and a self-hosted alternative to GitHub⁷, GitLab nowadays aims to be “the first single application for the entire DevOps lifecycle”(GitLab Inc. 2019b).

The usage of GIT repositories already supports the diversion of project code to branches for separate tiers in the development process and tagging commits as versioned releases as shown in figure 3. To prevent accidental code changes on higher tier branches, GitLab offers a feature to restrict pushes or accepting of merge requests for certain branches to project maintainers. The creation of specific tags, like versioning tags in the form “v-*” can be restricted, too. (ibid.)

For automation of tests, builds and deployment, GitLab comes with an integrated CI/CD system. If enabled for a project, it starts a new pipeline on every change in the repository. A pipeline is a list of integration or deployment jobs to execute for a certain change. These jobs are defined as shell scripts in a specific file called “.gitlab-ci.yml” in the root folder of the project’s code repository. GitLab CI runner daemons that are connected to the project pick up jobs from the pipeline and execute the contained commands either as shell script on the runners’ system or inside Docker containers. As context for the execution, they always pull a full copy of the project repository and the change the pipeline was created for (e.g. a specific commit or tag). In this context, the

⁶<https://git-scm.com>

⁷<https://github.com>

job scripts perform several actions as defined by the job configuration, e.g. to run tests, build the application or deploy on target servers for the different development process tiers. When all commands for all jobs in the pipeline have been successfully executed, the pipeline is considered as succeeded. (GitLab Inc. 2019b)

Using GitLab CI runners with Docker, developers can define the docker image to use for executing the job script. Thus, automated tests can be executed in the very same run-time environment that will later be used to create the application image and run the web application in production. If tests fail in the development branch, they will most likely do so on the customer's system, too. If identified as defective in this way, code can be prevented of being merged to other (maybe higher tier) branches, using GitLabs project setting "Merge when pipeline succeeds". This prevents branches with failed pipelines from being merged. (ibid.)

In this combination, developers without permission to push changes directly to higher tier branches have to take care of writing code that passes the pipeline to be able to merge it to higher level tier branches. Project maintainer with permission to use protected tags can trigger versioned production releases. An attempt to automate the deployment process as shown in figure 5 is described in section 6.

5.2. Docker

The Docker engine is a containerisation platform, that gives "developers and IT the freedom to build, manage and secure business-critical applications without the fear of technology or infrastructure lock-in"(Docker Inc. 2019d).

Unlike virtualisation techniques, a container is not a virtualised hardware environment running its own operating system (OS), it is rather a virtualisation of the OS itself (as shown by figure 8). Upon that, containers usually are used to start just one single service. Therefore, the template used to start the container (the docker image) only needs to contain only the libraries required to start this single application. (Docker Inc. 2019c)

To get an own application up and running with docker, there are three main possibilities to choose from:

Figure 8: Parallel execution of applications in containerised environment (left) vs. execution of entire operating systems in virtualised environment (right)
(Docker Inc. 2019c)

1. Build own container image from scratch
The self-built image must contain the whole system environment the application needs to be started (Docker Inc. 2019a)
2. Use an existing image as system environment
Available images from docker hub⁸ (e.g. ubuntu, node, tomcat) come with typical libraries and tooling for a certain Linux distribution, running node applications or an application server like tomcat.
The individual application is started with its folder mounted as volume into the container and, if required, altering the containers startup command.
3. Create an application image based on an existing image
By copying the code of the application and installing further requirements (e.g. node modules⁹) into an existing image, developers can create their own turnkey images for running the application on any computer running Docker.

Because it is very hard to collect all required tools and libraries for an application to start in an independent environment, for automation in software testing and deployment, the options 2 and 3 are to be preferred.

Running an application mounted into an existing image that provides the system environment can be set up very fast. Being mounted from the hosts hard drive, the application's code can still easily be examined and modified. Thus it is an ideal solution for frequent development releases (as the application is still debuggable) or testing the code in an automated GitLab CI pipeline as described in sections 6.2.1 and 6.2.2.

⁸<https://hub.docker.com/>

⁹<https://npmjs.com>

For deploying the application on the customer’s servers it would still require a manual deployment of the application folder.

On the other hand, option 3, while being more complex in design and more protracted in execution, requires no more manual deployment of application code. The application image, created upon an existing base image, contains all required project and vendor code to immediately start the application on any docker host machine. Therefore, updating the image on the customer’s server and restarting the application container afterwards are the only steps to perform for the deploying a new version of the application. For ease in deployment to the target systems, the self-built image can be pushed to a public¹⁰ or private¹¹ docker registry, a kind of software catalogue for docker images. The example project SMILe uses this approach to deploy release candidates and production releases using a private registry as described in section 6.2.6.

Figure 9: Deployment of an application with two required containers (node application server and database server) and required volumes for data persistence using single docker commands (left, simplified command parameters) vs. using docker-compose to start up a pre-configured application stack (right)

Especially for applications that consist of several services, e.g. application server and database, the creation and operation of required docker containers becomes a list of many commands with lots of parameters. “docker-compose” as a tool for multi-container application management offers the ability, to start an application with an entire, pre-defined stack of containers with a single command. This definition file can be seen as an environment specification for the application, containing required containers, published

¹⁰<https://hub.docker.com>

¹¹<https://docs.docker.com/registry/>

ports and volumes mounted into the containers. Figure 9 compares manual starting of an application and database container to the start commands using docker-compose. Thus, for lesser complexity of the deployment scripts and for a documented run-time environment of the deployed application, the applied part of this work uses docker-compose to start and stop the application deployed on the target servers. (Docker Inc. 2019b)

With Docker Content Trust (DCT)¹² the containerisation engine further offers a feature to cryptographically sign images after creation and verify them on the target servers after transferral over an insecure medium like the internet. Being automatable, code signing can be performed by distinct jobs during the CI pipeline, signing only successfully tested or manually verified and tagged builds (see section 6.2.3 and 6.2.6). (Docker Inc. 2018a) With a restriction of merging code to high-level tier branches as the master branch and the use of protected versioning tags to project maintainers, it is assured, that only tested and verified code gets signed for production. Thereby a production environment that is configured to use valid signed images only, is protected from updating an application with code that is insufficiently tested, built for testing purpose or modified on the wire during transferral to the target server. (Docker Inc. 2018b)

6. CI/CD with GitLab CI and docker

This section describes a practical approach to test and deploy a JavaScript application using GitLab and Docker. Being part of the previously introduced project SMILe, it maps the process for automated testing and deployment using GitLab CI as shown by figure 5. Therefore, it aims to meet the requirements of customer and developers as listed in section 2 in all four tiers of the development process.

6.1. Prerequisites

In order to use GitLab and Docker for automated tests and deployments of the JavaScript application as well as further support of the development team while meeting all previous

¹²https://docs.docker.com/engine/security/trust/content_trust/

noted requirements, there are some prerequisites to be met. These can be divided into requirements on project or infrastructure level as shown below. When they are fulfilled, the implementation of the CI/CD process described in the sections below can be applied to the project.

DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_REPOSITORY_PASSPHRASE	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
REGISTRY_PASS	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
REGISTRY_URL	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
REGISTRY_USER	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
STAGING_PRIVATE_KEY	*****	Protected	<input type="checkbox"/>
TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
TRUST_REPOSITORY_USER	*****	Protected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 10: Required GitLab CI environment variables configured on GitLab project level for use in CI job scripts, explained on usage in the sections below

Project requirements

1. Using GIT

The project uses GIT for version control and a GitLab server for contribution

2. Protected branches

Allow only maintainers to push code to branch dev and merge code to branch master

3. Protected tags

Allow maintainers only to use versioning tags in the format “v-*”

4. Restrict merge requests to pipelines

Allow only successfully tested code to be merged to other branches

5. Environment variables for CI pipeline

Project-specific information, like image names, user names, keys, and passwords are specified as GitLab CI environment variables (available for use in CI job scripts) like shown in figure 10 (GitLab Inc. 2018a)

Infrastructure requirements

1. **GitLab CI Docker runner**

In order to execute CI jobs inside Docker containers, at least one CI Docker runner must be connected to the GitLab server. Furthermore, to build own docker images from inside docker, the runner must be allowed to run “privileged”, being allowed to access the docker engine itself from inside the container. (GitLab Inc. 2019a)

2. **Docker on target servers**

On all target machines for dev, stable and production deployments, Docker Community Engine needs to be installed at least in version 17.12 (introduction of content trust).

As being used for starting and stopping defined container environments, docker-compose must be available on the servers, too.

3. **Docker Registry**

The project SMILe uses a private Docker registry to publish images for deployment. This is optional. The official docker hub^a can be used, too.

4. **Docker Notary**

The official docker notary service for content trust is bound to accounts on the official docker registry. Thus, for project SMILe, a private notary service is used.

5. **Deployment User on target servers**

The deployment user needs SSH access to the target servers using key authentication and must have permission to manage the docker instance using `docker` and `docker-compose` commands.

6. **Enforce Content Trust in production**

Setting the environment variables for DCT, only images with valid signatures from a notary server are accepted by the docker daemon. (Docker Inc. 2018a)

^a<https://hub.docker.com>

6.2. Defining the Stages for the CI Pipeline

The CI/CD process that is needed to be implemented for the described deployment process consists of six distinct parts. Because the code repository shall no longer contain untested code, code testing and linting needs to be done on every code change in any branch of the project repository. For first manual tests of merged features contributed by different developers, changes on the dev branch are deployed to a development server. On the master branch, code changes trigger the building of a docker image containing the application and all dependencies including running tests using the built image and pushing it as release candidate to a private docker image registry. Afterwards, this

Figure 11: Resulting GitLab CI process based on the planned deployment process from figure 5

release candidate is deployed to a production-like environment using the previous built image. At last, upon creation of a new versioning tag, the release candidate image is signed as stable for production using DCT and finally deployed on the production machines. The jobs for GitLab CI, resulting from this process, are shown in figure 11 and described in detail in the sections below.

Because GitLab executes defined jobs in a random order and, if there are multiple CI runners available, in parallel, too, the CI configuration first needs to introduce three stages as planned in figure 11. CI stages are always executed serial, requiring all jobs of a previous stage to succeed. Thus it can be assured, that no images are built or code is deployed if the code tests failed. Listing 1 states the configuration of these stages along with the definition of a default docker image to use, e.g. for running tests in a production-like runtime environment.

```

1 | image: node:8.9-alpine
2 | stages:

```

```
3 | - test
4 | - build
5 | - deploy
```

Listing 1: Default docker image and definition of stages for serial job execution, see appendix A.1 for full configuration file

6.2.1. Testing of new code

The first step in the automated deployment pipeline is the most important one to ensure code quality in the project's code base. Presuming a configuration for code linting and a test suite with sufficient test coverage for the code base, its goal is to check every code change for errors. In the Project SMILe, there are commands defined in the project's package.json file that execute code linting (`yarn lint`) and run the test suite (`yarn tests`).

For both jobs, Listing 2 shows the installation of requirements in a `before_script` block (used to set up the environment for the actual CI script) and highlighted the execution of linting and testing commands. As being defined in the first CI stage (`test`), any other CI jobs must wait for this phase to succeed. Running for all branches in the repository, its failure further blocks merge requests for faulty code to other branches.

```
13 | lint:
14 |   stage: test
15 |   before_script:
16 |     - yarn
17 |   script:
18 |     - yarn lint
19 | test:
20 |   stage: test
21 |   before_script:
22 |     - yarn
23 |   script:
24 |     - yarn tests
```

Listing 2: Testing and linting of every code push, excerpt from listing 15 in A.1

6.2.2. Deploying of the source code

According to the process plan from figure 11, every code change on the development branch shall lead to a new source code deployment of the application. To ensure this job is only executed for the desired branch, its configuration in Listing 3 makes use of the field “only” that is used to restrict jobs to a given list of branch or tag names (GitLab Inc. 2018b).

Using a different docker image than the project’s default, the setup script in the “before_script” block installs and configures required tools. It further adds the private key of the deployment user that is available from an environment variable (due to the configuration as GitLab CI Variable) to the SSH configuration inside the container (highlighted in Listing 3, line 92).

The main job script finally stops the running application, moves its folder to enable manual rollbacks, copies the whole project code to the development server and restarts the application using docker compose as highlighted in the script block of Listing 3.

```

83  image: debian:latest
84  stage: deploy
85  only:
86  - dev
87  before_script:
88  - 'which ssh-agent || ( apt-get update -y && apt-get install
    ↪ openssh-client -y )'
89  - mkdir -p ~/.ssh
90  - eval $(ssh-agent -s)
91  - '[[ -f /.dockerenv ]] && echo -e "Host *\n\tStrictHostKeyChecking
    ↪ no\n\n" > ~/.ssh/config'
92  - ssh-add <(echo "$STAGING_PRIVATE_KEY")
93  - apt-get install rsync -y
94  script:
95  - ssh user@dev.server.com "mkdir -p ~/deploy/stage/new"
96  - rsync -ravq -e "ssh" --exclude='.git/' --exclude='.gitlab-ci.yml'
    ↪ --delete-excluded ./user@dev.server.com:~/deploy/stage/new
97  - ssh user@dev.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stage/current &&
    ↪ docker-compose down || true"
98  - ssh user@dev.server.com "rm -r ~/deploy/stage/old || true"
99  - ssh user@dev.server.com "mv ~/deploy/stage/current
    ↪ ~/deploy/stage/old || true"
100 - ssh user@dev.server.com "mv ~/deploy/stage/new
    ↪ ~/deploy/stage/current"

```

```

101 | - ssh user@dev.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stage/current &&
    | ↪ docker-compose up -d"

```

Listing 3: Setup ssh deployment key, copy source files to development server and (re-)start the development docker container, excerpt from listing 15 in A.1

The compose file being used for starting the development version of the application, shown as excerpt in Listing 4, does not define a docker image to use. The build option that is used instead, triggers the building of an own docker image based on the build instructions defined in a provided Dockerfile.

```

4 |     build:
5 |         context: .
6 |         args:
7 |             APP_DIR: ${APP_DIR}

```

Listing 4: Configuration to build image from Dockerfile on first container start, excerpt from listing 16 in A.2

Listing 5 shows the build instructions used to create the docker image for development. Beside creating required directories and setting permissions, it defines as the base image to inherit from the same image that has been used as default image for the test jobs in section 6.2.1 before. This ensures, that code being successfully tested previously will run in the environment provided by this docker image, too.

```

1 | FROM node:8.9-alpine
2 | LABEL maintainer="michael.fuermann@hs-augsburg.de"
3 | RUN apk add --no-cache tini git
4 | ARG APP_DIR
5 | RUN mkdir -p ${APP_DIR}/build && \
6 |     mkdir -p ${APP_DIR}/node_modules && \
7 |     mkdir -p /home/node/.cache/yarn && \
8 |     chown node:node -R ${APP_DIR} /home/node
9 | USER node
10 | ENTRYPOINT ["/sbin/tini", "--"]

```

Listing 5: Build instructions for the container running the application in development

After the image creation has finished, docker compose automatically starts the application by running the command as defined in the docker-compose file with the application's source code folder mounted as volume into the container (fields "command" and "volumes" in Listing 6). For development purpose, the start command consists of

multiple steps to install dependencies, migrate and seed the database (if not exist) and start the application in development mode. Finally, the whole list of ports required for development (e.g. webpack server, debuggers, smartphone emulators) are published for connections from outside into the container.

```
14     volumes:
15         - ./${APP_DIR}
16         - ${APP_DIR}/build
17         - ${APP_DIR}/node_modules
18     working_dir: ${APP_DIR}
19     user: node
20     command: >
21         sh -c '
22         yarn &&
23         (test -f dev-db.sqlite3 || yarn seed) &&
24         exec yarn watch
25         '
26     ports:
27         - 3000:3000
28         - 3010:3010
29         - 3020:3020
30         - 8080:8080
31         - 19000:19000
32         - 19001:19001
```

Listing 6: Mounted source folders, container start command and published ports for development, excerpt from listing 16 in A.2

Because being deployed as source code mounted into an application server container, this release is still debuggable on the target server in the case of errors. The source files of the project are still mutable and independent of the docker container that runs the application. Nonetheless, because being started with a fresh checkout from the development branch on every code change, dependencies have to be installed on every development release, too, as well as migrating and seeding a fresh development database. Thus it can take some time until the development server is started again, but it ensures to have a clean and reproducible application setup for manual testing and debugging for every newly added feature.

6.2.3. Building the app image

As demanded in section 2, the deployment to production should be reliable and repeatable whilst requiring a minimum amount of manual effort. This can be realised, by creating a package that contains the application code and all required dependencies to start it immediately after deployment. The plan in figure 11 therefore contains a CI job to build an own docker image for each change on the master branch. After building, this image can be used for manual tests in a production-like environment as described in section 6.2.4. Deployed into production (see section 6.2.6) the application behaves the same thanks to the containerised environment.

Because the process of building Docker images needs to interact with the docker daemon itself, the CI job for building the application image uses a model called “Docker in Docker (DinD)”. In order for the docker client inside the container to communicate with the daemon on the host machine, the GitLab CI runner needs to be configured to execute runner containers in privileged mode. The lines 33 and 37 to 41 in Listing 7 show the additional required configuration for the CI job to use DinD. (GitLab Inc. 2019a)

The goal of this process step is to publish an image and sign it as the latest image built from CI. So the `before_script` shown in Listing 7 first performs a login sequence to the private Docker registry. To be able to sign images, it further places the private key of a signing user in dockers trust key directory and loads it to the docker trust client. All URLs, credentials, filenames, and keys are provided as environment variables from GitLabs CI Variable configuration as listed in section 6.1.

```
33  image: docker
34  stage: build
35  only:
36  - master
37  variables:
38    DOCKER_HOST: tcp://docker:2375/
39    DOCKER_DRIVER: overlay2
40  services:
41  - docker:dind
42  before_script:
43  - echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login $REGISTRY_URL -u $REGISTRY_USER
  ↪ --password-stdin
```

```

44 - mkdir -p ~/.docker/trust/private && echo "$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY" >
    ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME && chmod
    ↪ 600 ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME
45 - docker trust key load
    ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME --name
    ↪ $TRUST_REPOSITORY_USER
46 script:
47 - docker build -t $REGISTRY_URL/smile -f Dockerfile.stable .
48 - docker tag $REGISTRY_URL/smile $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
49 - docker push $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
50 - docker run --rm $REGISTRY_URL/smile yarn test
51 - docker trust sign $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest

```

Listing 7: Build, sign and publish latest application image on master branch, tag it as stable after running the test suite inside the image, excerpt from listing 15 in A.1

The jobs main script first builds the application image using a Dockerfile different from the previous one from section 6.2.2. As presented by Listing 8, it also inherits from the projects main image and creates a similar environment, but contains some further building steps (highlighted in the Listing). After copying the whole source directory into the container, it installs required libraries using `yarn` and also executes `yarn build`, the command for building the application for production. Thus, the image contains a copy of the application that is ready to be started without any further installation or compilation. Finally, the used Dockerfile defines the applications default port to be published and the start command that is used to check for database migrations and start the application.

After building the application like so, the CI script from Listing 7 tags it as the latest build and publishes it to the registry server. After successfully running the applications test suite, the latest build is further signed using the notary service. Thus, even if the tests fail, this state of the application build can be loaded and debugged by developers whilst it won't be deployed as release candidate because of the missing signature (see section 6.2.4 below).

```

1 FROM node:8.9-alpine
2 LABEL maintainer="michael.fuermann@hs-augsburg.de"
3 RUN apk add --no-cache tini git
4 COPY ./ /usr/src/app/
5 RUN mkdir -p /home/node/.cache/yarn && \
6     chown -R node:node /usr/src/app /home/node

```

```
7 USER node
8 RUN cd /usr/src/app && \
9     NODE_ENV=development yarn && \
10    yarn build
11 EXPOSE 8080
12 CMD sh -c 'cd /usr/src/app/packages/server && yarn migrate && yarn
13    ↪ start'
14 ENTRYPOINT ["/sbin/tini", "--"]
15 WORKDIR /usr/src/app
```

Listing 8: Build instructions for creating a turn-key ready application image containing all code and dependencies

6.2.4. Deploying the release candidate

For manual testing of new releases and presentation to the customer every code change on the master branch that succeeded the previous CI stages (test and build, see figure 11) leads to the deployment of a new release candidate.

To accomplish this, the CI job as shown in Listing 9, first configures an SSH client inside a Debian-based container as it did for deploying the development version in section 6.2.2. Further, it executes the authentication at the private Docker registry server via SSH on the target machine.

The job script itself pulls the actual application image being tagged as latest from the private registry. By setting the variables `DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST` and `DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER` it enforces docker to only accept images that have been signed using the private notary service. Thus, the image pulled from the registry is the latest one that was either signed by a project maintainer having a valid signer key or by the CI process' previous step after successfully running tests for the built image. Accidental tagged and published test builds by other developers are ignored.

After pulling the latest signed image from the docker registry, stopping the currently deployed release candidate and updating the docker-compose file on the target machine, docker-compose restarts the application services forcing recreation of the containers with the new version of the image.

```

103 | image: debian:latest
104 | stage: deploy
105 | only:
106 |   - master
107 | before_script:

```

[Configuration of ssh client as in section 6.2.2]

```

114 | - ssh user@rc.server.com "echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login $REGISTRY_URL
    | ↪ -u $REGISTRY_USER --password-stdin"
115 | script:
116 | - ssh user@rc.server.com "mkdir -p ~/deploy/stable"
117 | - ssh user@rc.server.com "DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
    | ↪ DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER=$DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER bash -c
    | ↪ 'docker image pull $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest'"
118 | - ssh user@rc.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stable && docker-compose -f
    | ↪ docker-compose.stable.yml down || true"
119 | - rsync -ravq -e "ssh"
    | ↪ ./docker-compose.stable.ymluser@rc.server.com:~/deploy/stable/
120 | - ssh user@rc.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stable && DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
    | ↪ bash -c 'docker-compose -f docker-compose.stable.yml up -d
    | ↪ --force-recreate'"

```

Listing 9: Testing and linting of every code push, see appendix A.1 for full configuration file

For the application container, the compose file in Listing 10 refers to the image that has been tagged “latest”, published and signed by the previous CI job. In contrast to development deployments, the release candidate only publishes the main HTTP port that is exposed by the image (see Dockerfile in Listing 8). It further defines a service dependency to the service “db” that is also defined in the compose file, referring to the official mariadb image as a database service. Thus, docker-compose will first wait for the MySQL service to be ready before the application is started, which avoids errors during startup because of a non-reachable database.

```

4 | image: autark.informatik.hs-augsburg.de:5000/smile:latest
5 | container_name: smile_stable
6 | depends_on:
7 |   - db
8 | ports:
9 |   - 8080:8080
19 | db:
20 |   image: mariadb

```

Listing 10: Image, published port and database service with service dependency for deployment of the release candidate, excerpt from listing 17 in A.2

Running this job most recently after each change on the master branch (according to figure 11) ensures to always have the latest stable application code deployed as the release candidate for manual testing or presentation. This is completely automated so far, without developers having to intervene manually in the deployment process.

6.2.5. Signing the image as stable for production

After a release candidate has been manually reviewed and tested, it is, according to the development process from section 1, marked as ready for deployment in production. The corresponding CI pipeline is triggered by a project maintainer adding a versioning tag on the master branch. This is realised by restricting the job to repository events starting with “v-” whilst ignoring regular pushes to branches, as shown in Listing 11.

```
55 | image: docker
56 | stage: build
57 | only:
58 | - /^v-.*\/
59 | except:
60 | - branches
```

Listing 11: Restrict the CI job to run only for versioning tags like v-0.0-5 or v-1rc, excerpt from listing 15 in A.1

The job script starts, as demonstrated by Listing 12 by setting `DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1`. This enforces all content pushed to or pulled from a docker registry to have a valid signature. Thus, having the private notary server already set by GitLab’s CI variables, pulling the image tagged as “latest” will download the latest tested and signed release candidate image. The final push after re-tagging the image as stable release automatically initiates the signing process with the notary service. Only after creating a valid signature the new tag is pushed to the registry and therefore the image marked as ready for production.

```
70 | script:
71 | - export DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
72 | - docker image pull $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
73 | - docker image tag $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
  ↪ $REGISTRY_URL/smile:stable
74 | - docker push $REGISTRY_URL/smile:stable
```

Listing 12: Re-tag the latest release candidate as stable and automatically sign it enforced by setting `DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST`, requires configuration for registry and notary signer as in Listing 7, excerpt from listing 15 in A.1

Unfortunately, this procedure has a pitfall. Because the latest built release candidate is used instead of building a new image, the maintainer must pay attention to only create a versioning tag on the very last commit on the master branch having a successfully executed GitLab CI building pipeline. Otherwise, people might get confused by version mismatches between the tagged release commits and actually contained code in the built docker images. But being limited in usage for the maintainer (see section 6.1) the risk of versioning tags being set wrong should be rather low.

6.2.6. Deploying the app to production

Finally, deploying the application on the customer’s production machine requires only a clear amount of commands to be executed. These, as described in Listing 13 are quite similar to the commands used to deploy the release candidate in section 6.2.4. The list starts with setting required variables for DCT and pulling the latest signed stable image. After using the current compose file for stopping the service, it gets updated to changes for the latest release (if any). The configuration contained in the compose file is quite similar to the deployment of the release candidate. It only differs in the used application image, referring to the tag “stable” instead of “latest” as shown by Listing 14. Starting the services again while recreating its containers from the new image finally updates the application to the latest stable build. For an example of a CI job executing these commands on a remote machine, please refer to appendix A.1.

```

1      export DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
2      export DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER=https://_
        ↪ address.of.notary.service
3      docker pull address.of.registry/smile.stable
4      docker-compose -f docker-compose.prod.yml down
5      # Copy new composefile to target machine if changed
6      docker-compose -f docker-compose.prod.yml up -d
        ↪ --force-recreate

```

Listing 13: Stop, update and start the application in production with enforcement to validate signatures using the private notary service. See 15 for the corresponding CI job definition “`deploy_prod`”, excerpt from listing in A.1

```
4 |     image: autark.informatik.hs-augsburg.de:5000/smile:stable
5 |     container_name: smile_prod
6 |     depends_on:
7 |     - db
8 |     ports:
9 |     - 8080:8080
```

Listing 14: Image, published port and db service dependency for deployment in production, excerpt from listing 18 in A.2

Unfortunately, the fully automated CI approach cannot be used for the introduced project SMILE. Running behind the firewall of the clinical data centre, the GitLab CI runner cannot establish a SSH connection to the production server. One approach to keep the deployment automated is, to include a helper for automated updates into the compose file. Applications like watchtower¹³ periodically check the images used by other containers for updates. Thus, after deploying and signing a new stable version of the application, it would be picked up and applied in production automatically. Being neither able to update the compose file on changes nor controlled by the CI process as demanded in section 2 (running independently after the first deployment), this is also not a suitable solution for production deployment in the mentioned project.

Therefore, it requires an administrator on the customer’s side or a developer having access to the production server by firewall authentication or VPN, to execute the steps described in Listing 13 by hand.

7. Conclusion

To conclude this work, this section first analyses to what extent the proposed CI/CDE process for the sample project SMILE meets the requirements described in section 2, evaluates the use of automation for different kinds of tasks in the process and finally describes unresolved challenges and topics for follow up works.

¹³<https://hub.docker.com/r/v2tec/watchtower>

7.1. Matching requirements and approach

After presenting the designed process for deployment automation for the example project SMILe in section 6, the following lines determine, if it meets the demands that have been noted in section 2. Therefore, advantages and downsides of the described approach will be explained and mapped to single items of the demand list to check, whether all items as required by developers and customer are fulfilled.

Because all steps of the introduced solution from section 6 are merely an automation of test, build and deploy tasks from the development teams' existing 4-tier development process (Figure 11), performing suitable deployment strategies for development, release candidate and production releases, D-1 and D-6 can be considered fulfilled. Having the settings related to branch and tag protection in place, as required as prerequisite in section 6.1, this also applies for D-2, because of the enforcement for developers to merge their code from feature to development and finally to the master branch under the restriction to have runnable code and succeeding tests on all branches.

Leaving less manual work for deployment due to automation, it hence maximises the time for developers to work on the project itself and thus resolves D-5. Running convenient on the GitLab CI runner, testing every code change and deploying every change on a tier upon feature level further meets the demands from D-3 and D-4 for tests and deployments to happen as early and often as possible.

When it comes to deployment into production, the use of docker images containing the whole application reduces privileges required for deployment to commands for updating the application image and restarting the services with docker and docker-compose. Using this commands, one developer with access to the server via VPN can roll out a new version of the application whilst full administrative control over the systems can stay with the customer. This meets the customer's demands C-1 and C-2. Furthermore, because Docker is available for all major operating systems, the deployment is not operating system or environment dependent. Without any influence on the developers or the deployment process, the customer is free to use any modern server operating system in any desired configuration including storage systems and backup strategies. Thus, C-3 and C-4 can be considered fulfilled, too. At last the approach uses DCT to sign created images and enforces Docker on production machines to validate signatures

from a private notary service. This ensures the integrity of the deployed application on the customer's server and meets requirement C-5.

While the approach broadly meets all requirements, there still are caveats to point out. To enforce a last manual check of the application upon release, a project maintainer has to manually add a versioning tag on the master branch of the repository for creating a signed release, while taking care to only tag the most recent commit as explained in 6.2.5. Due to a multi factor VPN secured connections to the production server, the release must further be deployed by hand and thus requires manual interference. The requirements D-1 and D-5 therefore still leave space for optimizations. And finally, as can be seen by the whole section 6, setting up the automation process for CI/CD is very individual and complex to plan for the specific application and development team. Thus, it might take time in the beginning of each new project to set up and adjust the CI/CD pipeline, which basically contradicts D-3 and D-4 to test and deploy as early as possible, but nevertheless allows frequent tests and deployments during the development lifecycle of the application.

7.2. What to automate, or not

After successfully automating the integration and delivery workflow for the example project SMILe, some tasks turned out to be easier to automate than others and some steps are still executed manually that could theoretically be done by the CI/CD system.

The effort for automation of tasks, that run locally on the GitLab CI runner system with no other systems involved turned out to be quite low. Running the code tests for every change only requires the definition of a suitable image for the run-time environment. Further, providing build instructions in a docker file allows to build an application image as part of a CI job and to execute code tests for that image afterwards, too, as shown in section 6.2.3. Both possibilities report the introduction of faulty code into the repository that breaks the test suite and thus help to ensure code quality and integrity.

Pushing the built application image to a private repository server and creating a signature using Docker Content Trust and a notary service comprises a net expense comparable to the previously mentioned tasks. Practical, setting up these services on

own servers brings a lot of initial work and probably will not pay if being used by one project only. For single projects or small companies, a paid plan for private repositories on docker hub¹⁴ or commercial providers like quai.io¹⁵ might be an affordable alternative to self-managed docker repository and notary services.

Harder to automate were the steps required for the deployments. Releasing new versions of the application needs to take place not on the GitLab CI runner itself, but on target servers being independent of the job runners. Therefore, the main part of automated deployment tasks with GitLab and docker consists of copying files to or running commands on remote machines. This requires a ssh client to be installed and configured before running the job script as demonstrated in section 6.2.2. This configuration includes providing an authorised key for authentication on the target ssh server. For the deployment itself it must be determined, which files must be transferred and which commands have to be executed for a reliable process. In the example for the project SMILe, the deployment for development in section 6.2.2 was harder to achieve than for the release candidate in section 6.2.4. Deploying the application as source code, installing dependencies and seeding the database requires more sequential commands to be planned for automation than transferring the definition file for docker-compose, pulling the new image and restarting the services.

A step that was not automated in the proposed CI setup, is the final release to the production server, although being very similar to the deployment of a release candidate. Even if the machines running the CI jobs have no possibility to interact with the target server, section 6.2.6 proposed a solution for automation using a helper service that periodically checks for updated docker images and updates running containers. But in the scenario of a healthcare app with importance to the patients' well-being, the project team decided to keep the manual execution of production updates for direct controllability of the update process. Last, a further candidate for automation, that hasn't been mentioned by this work, because not being suitable for the development process in project SMILe, is the merging of code to a higher tier branch. While new implementations from feature branches should remain subject to manual code reviews, all changes on the dev branch could automatically be merged to master and finally

¹⁴<https://hub.docker.com>

¹⁵<https://quay.io/>

deployed to production with the prerequisite of a successfully completed CI test and deployment pipeline on each subsequent branch. Instead of CDE, this would finally realize a CD process, releasing every implemented feature automatically to production with no further manual interference (Shahin et al. 2017).

7.3. Outlook

While meeting all demands from developers and the customer as described in section 2, the example for CI/CDE with GitLab and Docker in the project SMILe, as presented in section 6, still leaves space for improvement by further works.

First, it provides a solution for deploying updates to the application. But if an update in production fails or introduces a critical bug, it might be convenient to have a job for reverting the deployed application to a previous version. This would further require to tag built application images in CI jobs by version numbers, so they can be referenced for up- or downgrade of deployed docker containers. Another improvement takes place in the manual approval of releases for deployment in production. As described in section 6.2.5, the proposed approach signs the latest built and tested application image as stable for production after a project maintainer adds a versioning tag to a commit in the code repository. Because the image is built for the latest commit on the master branch, but the signing job is triggered for versioning tags for any commit on any branch, this step is prone to human errors creating confusion about the image's content if tagged to a wrong commit. Unfortunately, during creation of this work, no solution for this issue was found.

Further research could also focus on testing of non-functional requirements using the automated CI pipeline. To ensure the application's performance for example, it could be feasible to run load tests with a deployed release candidate. Last, following a new trend named DevSecOps, automated security checks could be added to the CI pipeline, scanning for application dependencies or system libraries with known vulnerabilities¹⁶ or reviewing the source code itself for vulnerabilities with techniques like static code analysis¹⁷. As a result, the CI process would not only take care of reliable, repeatable

¹⁶Example vulnerability scanners: yarn audit for project dependencies, Anchore for docker images

¹⁷https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Static_Code_Analysis

and secured deployments but also support the creation of software with fewer security flaws within.

A. Appendix

A.1. GitLab CI configuration

```
1  image: node:8.9-alpine
2  stages:
3  - test
4  - build
5  - deploy
6
7
8  ## ----- ##
9  ##                               ##
10 ##   TESTING                       ##
11 ## ----- ##
12
13 lint:
14   stage: test
15   before_script:
16   - yarn
17   script:
18   - yarn lint
19 test:
20   stage: test
21   before_script:
22   - yarn
23   script:
24   - yarn tests
25
26
27 ## ----- ##
28 ##                               ##
29 ##   IMAGE BUILDING                 ##
30 ## ----- ##
31
32 build_image:
33   image: docker
34   stage: build
35   only:
36   - master
37   variables:
38     DOCKER_HOST: tcp://docker:2375/
```

```
39     DOCKER_DRIVER: overlay2
40 services:
41   - docker:dind
42 before_script:
43   - echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login $REGISTRY_URL -u $REGISTRY_USER
44     ↪ --password-stdin
45   - mkdir -p ~/.docker/trust/private && echo "$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY" >
46     ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME && chmod
47     ↪ 600 ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME
48   - docker trust key load
49     ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME --name
50     ↪ $TRUST_REPOSITORY_USER
51 script:
52   - docker build -t $REGISTRY_URL/smile -f Dockerfile.stable .
53   - docker tag $REGISTRY_URL/smile $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
54   - docker push $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
55   - docker run --rm $REGISTRY_URL/smile yarn test
56   - docker trust sign $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
57
58 sign_stable:
59   image: docker
60   stage: build
61   only:
62     - /~v-.* /
63   except:
64     - branches
65   variables:
66     DOCKER_HOST: tcp://docker:2375/
67     DOCKER_DRIVER: overlay2
68   services:
69     - docker:dind
70 before_script:
71   - echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login $REGISTRY_URL -u $REGISTRY_USER
72     ↪ --password-stdin
73   - mkdir -p ~/.docker/trust/private && echo "$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY" >
74     ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME && chmod
75     ↪ 600 ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME
76   - docker trust key load
77     ↪ ~/.docker/trust/private/$TRUST_REPOSITORY_KEY_FILENAME --name
78     ↪ $TRUST_REPOSITORY_USER
79 script:
80   - export DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
81   - docker image pull $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
82   - docker image tag $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest
83     ↪ $REGISTRY_URL/smile:stable
84   - docker push $REGISTRY_URL/smile:stable
```

```
77  ##-----##
78  ##                                ##
79  ##  DEPLOYMENT                    ##
80  ##-----##
81
82  deploy_dev:
83    image: debian:latest
84    stage: deploy
85    only:
86    - dev
87    before_script:
88    - 'which ssh-agent || ( apt-get update -y && apt-get install
      ↪ openssh-client -y )'
89    - mkdir -p ~/.ssh
90    - eval $(ssh-agent -s)
91    - '[[ -f /.dockerenv ]] && echo -e "Host *\n\tStrictHostKeyChecking
      ↪ no\n\n" > ~/.ssh/config'
92    - ssh-add <(echo "$STAGING_PRIVATE_KEY")
93    - apt-get install rsync -y
94    script:
95    - ssh user@dev.server.com "mkdir -p ~/deploy/stage/new"
96    - rsync -ravq -e "ssh" --exclude='.git/' --exclude='.gitlab-ci.yml'
      ↪ --delete-excluded ./user@dev.server.com:~/deploy/stage/new
97    - ssh user@dev.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stage/current &&
      ↪ docker-compose down || true"
98    - ssh user@dev.server.com "rm -r ~/deploy/stage/old || true"
99    - ssh user@dev.server.com "mv ~/deploy/stage/current
      ↪ ~/deploy/stage/old || true"
100   - ssh user@dev.server.com "mv ~/deploy/stage/new
      ↪ ~/deploy/stage/current"
101   - ssh user@dev.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stage/current &&
      ↪ docker-compose up -d"
102  deploy_rc:
103    image: debian:latest
104    stage: deploy
105    only:
106    - master
107    before_script:
108    - 'which ssh-agent || ( apt-get update -y && apt-get install
      ↪ openssh-client -y )'
109    - mkdir -p ~/.ssh
110    - eval $(ssh-agent -s)
111    - '[[ -f /.dockerenv ]] && echo -e "Host *\n\tStrictHostKeyChecking
      ↪ no\n\n" > ~/.ssh/config'
112    - ssh-add <(echo "$STAGING_PRIVATE_KEY")
113    - apt-get install rsync -y
114    - ssh user@rc.server.com "echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login
      ↪ $REGISTRY_URL -u $REGISTRY_USER --password-stdin"
115    script:
```

```

116 - ssh user@rc.server.com "mkdir -p ~/deploy/stable"
117 - ssh user@rc.server.com "DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
    ↪ DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER=$DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER bash -c
    ↪ 'docker image pull $REGISTRY_URL/smile:latest'"
118 - ssh user@rc.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stable && docker-compose -f
    ↪ docker-compose.stable.yml down || true"
119 - rsync -ravq -e "ssh"
    ↪ ./docker-compose.stable.ymluser@rc.server.com:~/deploy/stable/
120 - ssh user@rc.server.com "cd ~/deploy/stable &&
    ↪ DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1 bash -c 'docker-compose -f
    ↪ docker-compose.stable.yml up -d --force-recreate'"
121 deploy_prod:
122 image: debian:latest
123 stage: deploy
124 only:
125 - /~v-.* /
126 except:
127 - branches
128 before_script:
129 - 'which ssh-agent || ( apt-get update -y && apt-get install
    ↪ openssh-client -y )'
130 - mkdir -p ~/.ssh
131 - eval $(ssh-agent -s)
132 - '[[ -f /.dockerenv ]] && echo -e "Host *\n\tStrictHostKeyChecking
    ↪ no\n\n" > ~/.ssh/config'
133 - ssh-add <(echo "$STAGING_PRIVATE_KEY")
134 - apt-get install rsync -y
135 - ssh user@prod.server.com "echo $REGISTRY_PASS | docker login
    ↪ $REGISTRY_URL -u $REGISTRY_USER --password-stdin"
136 script:
137 - ssh user@prod.server.com "mkdir -p ~/deploy/prod"
138 - ssh user@prod.server.com "DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1
    ↪ DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER=$DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST_SERVER bash -c
    ↪ 'docker image pull $REGISTRY_URL/smile:stable'"
139 - ssh user@prod.server.com "cd ~/deploy/prod && docker-compose -f
    ↪ docker-compose.prod.yml down || true"
140 - rsync -ravq -e "ssh"
    ↪ ./docker-compose.prod.ymluser@prod.server.com:~/deploy/prod/
141 - ssh user@prod.server.com "cd ~/deploy/prod &&
    ↪ DOCKER_CONTENT_TRUST=1 bash -c 'docker-compose -f
    ↪ docker-compose.prod.yml up -d --force-recreate'"

```

Listing 15: .gitlab-ci.yml
Configuration file for GitLab CI

A.2. Compose definitions for running the application

```
1 version: '3'
2 services:
3   node:
4     build:
5       context: .
6       args:
7         APP_DIR: ${APP_DIR}
8     environment:
9       - NODE_ENV=development
10      - CI_LEVEL=dev
11     container_name: smile_dev
12     tty: true
13     stdin_open: true
14     volumes:
15       - ./${APP_DIR}
16       - ${APP_DIR}/build
17       - ${APP_DIR}/node_modules
18     working_dir: ${APP_DIR}
19     user: node
20     command: >
21       sh -c '
22         yarn &&
23         (test -f dev-db.sqlite3 || yarn seed) &&
24         exec yarn watch
25       '
26     ports:
27       - 3000:3000
28       - 3010:3010
29       - 3020:3020
30       - 8080:8080
31       - 19000:19000
32       - 19001:19001
```

Listing 16: docker-compose.yml - Compose file for running the application for development with mounted source directory

```
1 version: '3'
2 services:
3   stable:
4     image: autark.informatik.hs-augsburg.de:5000/smile:latest
5     container_name: smile_stable
6     depends_on:
7       - db
8     ports:
9       - 8080:8080
10    tty: true
11    stdin_open: true
12    user: node
```

```
13     environment:
14     - DB_CLIENT=mysql2
15     - DB_HOST=db
16     - DB_USER=db_user
17     - DB_PASSWORD=db_passwd
18     - DB_DATABASE=db_name
19 db:
20     image: mariadb
21     container_name: smile_stable_db
22     ports:
23     - 3306:3306
24     volumes:
25     - smile_stable_db:/var/lib/mysql
26     environment:
27     - MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD=passwd_for_root
28     - MYSQL_DATABASE=db_name
29     - MYSQL_USER=db_user
30     - MYSQL_PASSWORD=db_passwd
31 volumes:
32     smile_stable_db:
```

Listing 17: docker-compose.stable.yml

Compose file for running the application as release candidate in a production-like environment

```
1 version: '3'
2 services:
3   prod:
4     image: autark.informatik.hs-augsburg.de:5000/smile:stable
5     container_name: smile_prod
6     depends_on:
7     - db
8     ports:
9     - 8080:8080
10    tty: true
11    stdin_open: true
12    user: node
13    environment:
14    - DB_CLIENT=mysql2
15    - DB_HOST=db
16    - DB_USER=db_user
17    - DB_PASSWORD=db_passwd
18    - DB_DATABASE=db_name
19 db:
20    image: mariadb
21    container_name: smile_prod_db
22    ports:
23    - 3308:3306
24    volumes:
```

```
25 | - /var/lib/docker/custom_volumes/smile/db:/var/lib/mysql
26 | environment:
27 | - MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD=passwd_for_root
28 | - MYSQL_DATABASE=db_name
29 | - MYSQL_USER=db_user
30 | - MYSQL_PASSWORD=db_passwd
```

Listing 18: docker-compose.prod.yml
Compose file for running the application in production

A.3. Dockerfiles for building node server and application images

```
1 FROM node:8.9-alpine
2 LABEL maintainer="michael.fuermann@hs-augsburg.de"
3 RUN apk add --no-cache tini git
4 ARG APP_DIR
5 RUN mkdir -p ${APP_DIR}/build && \
6     mkdir -p ${APP_DIR}/node_modules && \
7     mkdir -p /home/node/.cache/yarn && \
8     chown node:node -R ${APP_DIR} /home/node
9 USER node
10 ENTRYPOINT ["/sbin/tini", "--"]
```

Listing 19: Dockerfile to build the node server container image for development, as shown before in Section 6.2.2, Listing 5

```
1 FROM node:8.9-alpine
2 LABEL maintainer="michael.fuermann@hs-augsburg.de"
3 RUN apk add --no-cache tini git
4 COPY ./ /usr/src/app/
5 RUN mkdir -p /home/node/.cache/yarn && \
6     chown -R node:node /usr/src/app /home/node
7 USER node
8 RUN cd /usr/src/app && \
9     NODE_ENV=development yarn && \
10    yarn build
11 EXPOSE 8080
12 CMD sh -c 'cd /usr/src/app/packages/server && yarn migrate && yarn
13 ↪ start'
14 ENTRYPOINT ["/sbin/tini", "--"]
15 WORKDIR /usr/src/app
```

Listing 20: Build instructions for creating a turn-key ready application image containing all code and dependencies, as shown before in Section 6.2.3, Listing ??

References

- 451 Research, Microsoft (Mar. 2017). *Level of on-premise private cloud use worldwide in 2017, by region*. Ed. by Statista. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/579537/worldwide-cloud-hosting-survey-on-premise-private-cloud-use/> (last reviewed at 03/03/2019).
- Bibi, Stamatia, Dimitrios Katsaros, and Panayiotis Bozanis (May 2012). “Business Application Acquisition: On-Premise or SaaS-Based Solutions?” In: *IEEE Software* 29.3, pp. 86–93. DOI: 10.1109/ms.2011.119.
- Docker Inc. (2018a). *Automation with content trust*. URL: https://docs.docker.com/engine/security/trust/trust_automation/ (last reviewed at 12/20/2018).
- (2018b). *Content trust in Docker*. URL: https://docs.docker.com/engine/security/trust/content_trust/#survey-of-typical-dct-operations (last reviewed at 12/20/2018).
 - (Mar. 22, 2019a). *Create a base image*. URL: <https://docs.docker.com/develop/develop-images/baseimages/> (last reviewed at 03/22/2019).
 - (Mar. 27, 2019b). *Overview of Docker Compose*. URL: <https://docs.docker.com/compose/overview/> (last reviewed at 03/27/2019).
 - (2019c). *What is a Container?* URL: <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container> (last reviewed at 03/05/2019).
 - (2019d). *Why Docker?* URL: <https://www.docker.com/why-docker> (last reviewed at 03/05/2019).
- Eurostat (Jan. 2018). *Use of cloud computing services across all enterprises in Germany in 2016, by cloud service*. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/879647/germany-use-of-cloud-computing-services-by-all-enterprises/> (last reviewed at 03/03/2019).
- GitLab Inc. (2018a). *GitLab CI/CD Variables*. URL: <https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/variables/> (last reviewed at 12/20/2018).
- (2018b). *GitLab Continuous Integration (GitLab CI/CD)*. URL: <https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/yaml/README.html> (last reviewed at 12/20/2018).
 - (2019a). *Building Docker images with GitLab CI/CD*. URL: https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/docker/using_docker_build.html (last reviewed at 03/10/2019).
 - (2019b). *Features*. URL: <https://about.gitlab.com/features/> (last reviewed at 03/05/2019).
- Jez Humble, David Farley (Dec. 21, 2010). *Continuous Delivery*. Addison Wesley. 512 pp. URL: https://www.ebook.de/de/product/9446498/jez_humble_david_farley_continuous_delivery.html.

- Sauce Labs; Dimensional Research (Feb. 2018). *Frequency of software build deployment worldwide, in 2018, current vs desired*. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/673403/worldwide-software-development-survey-deployment-frequency/> (last reviewed at 03/19/2019).
- Shahin, Mojtaba, Muhammad Ali Babar, and Liming Zhu (2017). “Continuous Integration, Delivery and Deployment: A Systematic Review on Approaches, Tools, Challenges and Practices”. In: *IEEE Access* 5, pp. 3909–3943. DOI: 10.1109/access.2017.2685629.
- Talwar, V., Qinyi Wu, C. Pu, Wenchang Yan, Gueyoung Jung, and D. Milojicic (June 20, 2005). “Comparison of Approaches to Service Deployment”. In: *25th IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS’05)*. IEEE. DOI: 10.1109/icdcs.2005.18.
- TEKsystems (Dec. 2018). *Technology initiatives deployment plans within organizations worldwide in 2019*. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/975268/worldwide-technology-initiatives-deployment-plans/> (last reviewed at 03/19/2019).

